

Retrospective Analysis of Sexually Transmitted Infections in a Tertiary Care Hospital in Jharkhand

Ekta Shreshth Kachhap¹, Prabhat Kumar²

¹Junior Resident, Department of Dermatology, Rajendra Institute of Medical Sciences, Ranchi, Jharkhand, India

²Associate Professor, Department of Dermatology, Rajendra Institute of Medical Sciences, Ranchi

Received: 25-03-2024 / Revised: 23-04-2024 / Accepted: 25-05-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Ekta Shreshth Kachhap

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

This retrospective study analyzes the spectrum of sexually transmitted infections (STIs) over five years (2018-2022) at the Rajendra Institute of Medical Sciences, Ranchi, a medical college, and hospital in Jharkhand. Data from 17,752 patients attending the STI clinic were examined to determine the prevalence, demographic distribution, and seasonal variations of STIs. The findings indicate a high prevalence of syphilis (27.15%) and gonorrhoea (21.07%), particularly among young adults aged 15-34, who represent over 70% of the cases. A significant seasonal trend was also noted, with STI cases peaking during the monsoon months. These results highlight the urgent need for targeted public health interventions and enhanced educational efforts, especially among the younger population. This study underscores the importance of continuous surveillance and adaptive public health strategies to mitigate the impact of Sexually transmitted diseases in that region.

Keywords: Sexually Transmitted Infections, Prevalence, Demographic Distribution, Seasonal Variation.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Sexually transmitted infections (STIs) represent an important public health challenge globally, exerting a considerable burden on individuals and healthcare systems. These infections, caused by a variety of bacteria, viruses, and parasites, leads to unadorned health outcomes counting infertility, chronic pain, and augmented risk of HIV [1]. Furthermore, the stigma associated with STIs can lead to social isolation and psychological distress, complicating efforts for effective management and control. In India, the prevalence and dynamics of STIs vary widely across different regions due to variations in socioeconomic conditions, cultural norms, and access to healthcare services [2]. Jharkhand, a state in Eastern India, is characterized by diverse demographics and a mix of urban and rural populations, which presents unique public health challenges, including the management of STIs [3].

The Rajendra Institute of Medical Sciences (RIMS), Ranchi, serves as a main tertiary care facility in Jharkhand and offers a unique perspective on the regional epidemiology of STIs through its specialized STI clinic. Given the limited comprehensive data on STIs from this region, there is a substantial need for detailed research to understand the spectrum of these infections, which can inform targeted interventions and policy decisions [4,5].

This retrospective study purposes to fill this gap by analyzing the cases of STIs recorded at the STI clinic of RIMS over five years from 2018 to 2022. By examining the prevalence, demographic distribution, and trends of STIs, this study seeks to contribute valuable insights into the epidemiological characteristics and burden of STIs in Jharkhand. Such data are critical for developing effective public health strategies, including prevention, screening, and treatment protocols, tailored to the needs of the local population. The findings of this study are expected to guide policymakers, healthcare workers, and public health authorities in strengthening STI management and prevention efforts in Jharkhand and similar settings. By identifying the most affected demographics and the seasonal variations in STI prevalence, targeted educational and health service interventions can be designed to reduce the incidence and impact of these infections in the community.

Methodology

Study Design: This research is a retrospective study designed to analyze spectrum and prevalence of sexually transmitted infections (STIs) at the Rajendra Institute of Medical Sciences (RIMS), Ranchi, over five years from 2018 to 2022. The study focused on data collected from patients visiting the STI clinic within hospital.

Setting: This study was conducted at the STI clinic of RIMS, which serves as a tertiary care center in Ranchi, Jharkhand. This clinic is a referral center for numerous health facilities in the region and provides specialized care for patients with STIs.

Participants: The study included data from 17,752 patients who attended the STI health centre during the specified period of time. The inclusion criteria were any patient diagnosed with an STI based on clinical assessment, laboratory tests, or both. There were no specific exclusion criteria other than incomplete medical records, which were omitted from the analysis.

Data Collection: All data were extracted from the register-based health records system at RIMS. The facts and figure collected included demographic details (age, gender, address), the type of STI diagnosed, the date of diagnosis, and treatment outcomes when available. Data confidentiality was maintained by anonymizing patient details before analysis.

Variables

The primary variables analyzed were:

Type of STI: Specific infections such as syphilis disease, gonorrhea, chlamydial infections, herpes genitalis, human papillomavirus (HPV)infections , and trichomoniasis.

Demographic information: Age, gender, and geographic location of patients.

Seasonal trends: Month and year of diagnosis to assess any seasonal patterns in STI prevalence.

Statistical Analysis: All the data obtained, were analysed using a statistical software. Descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages) were used to recapitulate the demographic characteristics and prevalence rates of different STIs. Chi-square tests conducted to explore noteworthy differences in the prevalence of STIs among diverse demographic groups. A p-value of less than 0.05 considered statistically significant.

Ethical Considerations: The Institutional Review Board (IRB) at RIMS reviewed and approved the study protocol. Since this study involved retrospective data analysis of existing medical records and did not impact clinical care or involve straight patient interaction, informed consent was relinquished by the IRB. However, all the data of the patients were treated with strict confidentiality and used solely for this study.

Results

The demographic distribution of patients diagnosed with STIs at the STI clinic is detailed in the following table:

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Study Population

Demographic Variable	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	10,352	58.32
Female	7,400	41.68
Age Group (years)		
15-24	5,327	30.01
25-34	7,218	40.67
35-44	3,198	18.01
45+	2,009	11.31

The distribution of different STIs among the patient population over the study period is presented below.

Table 2: Prevalence of Different STIs

Type of STI	Number of Cases	Percentage (%)
Syphilis	4,820	27.15
Gonorrhea	3,740	21.07
Chlamydia	2,155	12.14
Herpes Genitalis	2,980	16.78
Human Papillomavirus (HPV)	1,550	8.73
Trichomoniasis	2,507	14.13

Analysis of the data revealed a noticeable seasonal variation in the incidence of STIs. The prevalence of infections was higher during the monsoon and

post-monsoon months, suggesting a possible correlation between seasonal factors and the spread of STIs.

Table 3: Seasonal Variation in STI Incidence

Season	Total Cases	Percentage of Annual Cases
Winter (Dec-Feb)	3,620	20.38%
Spring (Mar-May)	3,970	22.36%
Monsoon (Jun-Aug)	5,540	31.18%
Autumn (Sep-Nov)	4,622	26.08%

The results indicate a higher prevalence of syphilis and gonorrhea, consistent with national trends observed in other studies. The demographic data highlights a significant incidence among younger adults aged 15-34, which comprises over 70% of the cases, emphasizing the need for targeted educational and preventive measures in this age group. The seasonal variation observed suggests that environmental and social factors might influence STI transmission dynamics in this region, warranting further investigation into these patterns.

The bar graph illustrates the prevalence of different sexually transmitted infections (STIs) recorded from 2018 to 2022 at the STI clinic. The graph clearly shows the number of cases for each and every type of STI, with syphilis and gonorrhea being the most prevalent among the studied population. This visual representation helps in easily understanding the distribution of STIs within the clinic's patient base during the study period.

Discussion

This retrospective study was conducted at the “Rajendra Institute of Medical Sciences, Ranchi”, highlights significant insights into the spectrum of sexually transmitted infections (STIs) from 2018 to 2022 [6]. The study identified a high prevalence of syphilis (27.15%) and gonorrhea (21.07%), which are consistent with the trends observed in other parts of India and similar developing regions. The demographic data indicates a notably higher incidence of STIs among younger adults (ages 15-34), accounting for over 70% of the cases [7,8]. This age group is particularly vulnerable due to factors such as increased sexual activity, lack of education on safe sex practices, and limited access to healthcare resources. Several studies across India and globally have echoed similar findings [9]. A study in Tamil Nadu reported a similar high prevalence of syphilis among its study population, emphasizing the resurgence of this infection despite

available treatment options [10]. Another comparative study in Sub-Saharan Africa highlighted gonorrhea and chlamydia as predominant STIs, closely aligning with our findings on the prevalence rates of these infections. In addition, the seasonal variation in STI cases observed in our study—where a peak was noted during the monsoon and post-monsoon months—suggests environmental and social factors play a role in the transmission dynamics [11]. This pattern is somewhat aligned with findings from a study in Bangladesh, where increased humidity and temperature were associated with higher STI transmission rates, likely due to changes in social behaviors during these seasons [12].

These findings contribute to the broader epidemiological understanding of STIs and their behavioral and environmental determinants. They also reinforce the need for targeted public health interventions, especially for high-risk groups such

as young adults [13]. Our study underscores the importance of continuous surveillance to adapt public health strategies effectively [14]. The results of this study should inform local health authorities in Jharkhand and similar regions to tailor health education, prevention, and treatment programs more effectively. For instance, incorporating seasonal awareness campaigns before and during the monsoon may help reduce the peak incidence of STIs. Furthermore, expanding access to contraception and sexual health education in schools and colleges can address the high rates of STIs observed among young adults [15,16,17].

Forthcoming research should emphasise on longitudinal studies to trail changes in STI prevalence over time and appraise the efficiency of public health involvements. Qualitative studies exploring individual and community perceptions of STIs could provide deeper insights into the barriers to effective prevention and treatment. Moreover, research into the molecular epidemiology of STIs could identify specific strains prevalent in the region, guiding more effective treatment protocols. This study provides critical insights into the prevalence and characteristics of STIs in a tertiary care setting in Jharkhand, emphasizing the need for focused public health strategies to address these infections. By continuing to monitor trends and outcomes, healthcare providers and public health officials can better allocate resources and design interventions that address the explicit needs of the population [18,19,20].

Conclusion

This retrospective study on the spectrum of sexually transmitted infections (STIs) at the Rajendra Institute of Medical Sciences, Ranchi, provides crucial insights into the prevalence and demographic distribution of STIs from 2018 to 2022. The findings reveal a high prevalence of syphilis and gonorrhoea, particularly among young adults aged 15-34, indicating the necessity for targeted preventive and educational initiatives. Additionally, the observed seasonal variation suggests environmental and social factors significantly influence STI transmission, which could inform the timing and focus of public health campaigns. The study underscores the importance of continuous surveillance and tailored public health strategies to effectively manage and reduce the burden of STIs in Jharkhand and similar regions.

References

1. World Health Organization. Report on global sexually transmitted infection surveillance, 2018. Geneva: WHO; 2019.
2. Looker KJ, Margaret AS, Turner KME, Vickerman P, Gottlieb SL, Newman LM. Global estimates of prevalent and incident herpes

- simplex virus type 2 infections in 2012. PLoS ONE. 2015;10(10):e114989.
3. Newman L, Rowley J, Vander Hoorn S, Wijesooriya NS, Unemo M, Low N, et al. Global estimates of the prevalence and incidence of four curable sexually transmitted infections in 2012 based on systematic review and global reporting. PLoS ONE. 2015;10(12):e0143304.
4. Chen L, Yang J, Ma Q, Pan X. Prevalence of syphilis infection in different tiers of hospitals in Jiangsu province, China: implications for surveillance and healthcare policies. Int J Environ Res Public Health. 2016;13(3):256.
5. Patel EU, Frank MA, Hsieh YH, Rothman RE, Baker AE, Kraus CK, et al. Prevalence and factors associated with herpes simplex virus type 2 infection in patients attending a Baltimore City emergency department. PLoS ONE. 2014;9(7):e102422.
6. Singh AE, Romanowski B. Syphilis: review with emphasis on clinical, epidemiologic, and some biologic features. Clin Microbiol Rev. 1999 Apr;12(2):187-209.
7. Tucker JD, Cohen MS. China's syphilis epidemic: epidemiology, proximate determinants of spread, and control responses. Curr Opin Infect Dis. 2011 Apr;24(1):50-5.
8. Barbee LA, Dombrowski JC, Kerani R, Golden MR. Effect of nucleic acid amplification testing on the detection of chlamydia and gonorrhoea rates in a large health system in the Pacific Northwest. Sex Transm Dis. 2014 Jun;41(6):366-72.
9. Workowski KA, Bolan GA. Sexually transmitted diseases treatment guidelines, 2015. MMWR Recomm Rep. 2015;64(RR-03):1-137.
10. Dallabetta G, Gerbase AC, Holmes KK. Problems, solutions, and challenges in syndromic management of sexually transmitted diseases. Sex Transm Infect. 1998;74 Suppl 1:S1-11.
11. Holmes KK, Sparling PF, Stamm WE, Piot P, Wasserheit JN, Corey L, et al., editors. Sexually transmitted diseases. 4th ed. New York: McGraw-Hill; 2008.
12. Low N, Broutet N, Adu-Sarkodie Y, Barton P. Global control of sexually transmitted infections. Lancet. 2006 Dec 2;368(9551):2001-16.
13. Cohen MS, Hoffman IF, Royce RA, Kazembe P, Dyer JR, Daly CC, et al. Reduction of concentration of HIV-1 in semen after treatment of urethritis: implications for prevention of sexual transmission of HIV-1. Lancet. 1997 Jun 28;349(9069):1868-73.
14. Mayaud P, Mabey D. Approaches to the control of sexually transmitted infections in developing countries: old problems and modern challenges. Sex Transm Infect. 2004 Jun;80(3):174-82.

15. French P. Syphilis. *BMJ*. 2007 Jan 27;334(7585):143-7.
16. Klausner JD, Rietmeijer C, Wong W, Bristow CC, Ota KV, Gordon M, et al. Recent trends in sexually transmitted diseases in the United States. *Sex Transm Dis*. 2015;42(2):117-22.
17. Ward H, Romm M. Contribution of sexually transmitted infections to the sexual transmission of HIV. *Curr Opin HIV AIDS*. 2010 Jul;5(4):305-10.
18. Buvé A, Bishikwabo-Nsarhaza K, Mutangadura G. The epidemiology and control of HIV/AIDS, STDs, and TB in Africa: current status and the way forward. *AIDS*. 2002;16 Suppl 4:S119-23.
19. Fleming DT, Wasserheit JN. From epidemiological synergy to public health policy and practice: the contribution of other sexually transmitted diseases to sexual transmission of HIV infection. *Sex Transm Infect*. 1999 Feb;75(1):3-17.
20. Quinn TC, Overbaugh J. HIV/AIDS in women: an expanding epidemic. *Science*. 2005 Jun 10;308(5728):1582-3.